

Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds : Part XXVIII. Synthesis of 1,3-diaryl-5-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamyl- benzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H,5H)-pyrimidinediones and Their *in vitro* Screening

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Four series of 1,3-diaryl-5-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamyl-benzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6(1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones have been synthesised by coupling 1,3-diaryldihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones with a number of diazotised sulphonamide bases. The antibacterial properties of these compounds were evaluated and some of these were found to exhibit marked activity.

ENCOURAGED by the results obtained during the course of our earlier work on the synthesis and screening of some 1,3-diaryl-5-(aryazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6(1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones and in view of the fact that hardly any work has been reported on the screening of corresponding 5-sulphonamido-benzeneazo derivatives,^{2,8} it was thought of interest to synthesise, new pyrimidinediones having the sulphonamide residue attached through an azo linkage at position 5 with the hope that the resulting products may prove to be better antibacterials.

The present paper describes the synthesis and *in vitro* screening of 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-methylphenyl)-, 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-bromophenyl)-1,3-bis(*p*-bromophenyl)- and 1-(*p*-bromophenyl)-3-(*p*-methylphenyl)-5-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H)-pyrimidinediones of the type I. These were prepared by coupling 1,3-diaryldihydro-2-thioxo-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones with different diazotised sulphonamide bases. The homogeneity and purity of these compounds were tested by GLC and the structures confirmed by elemental analysis, IR and NMR spectral data.

IR spectra of different 1,3-diaryldihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidine diones show a doublet in the region 1693-1730 cm^{-1} , a sharp (m) peak around 1064 cm^{-1} and a peak around 1475-1485 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to carbonyl frequency, C=S stretching vibrations and C=S bonding in association with C-N vibrational modes respectively. NMR spectra of the above compounds show a singlet around 4.0 δ which could be attributed to $-\text{COCH}_2\text{CO}$; the absence of NH protons in NMR spectra further confirmed their cyclic structures.

In the IR spectra of 1,3-diaryl-5-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H,

5H)-pyrimidinediones, the bands in the region 1587-1610 cm^{-1} could be assigned to N=N stretching vibrations. Absence of any signal for NH protons in the NMR spectra further confirmed the azo structure of these compounds. The peaks in the range of 1250-1280 cm^{-1} and 1080-1090 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of different azo compounds represent the respective asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of vibrations of S=O from sulphonamido group.

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Experimental

Different 1,3-diaryldihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H,5H)-pyrimidinediones required for this work have been synthesised in the manner reported earlier¹.

Synthesis of 1-phenyl-3-(p-methylphenyl)-5-(N-phenyl p-sulphamylbenzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H) pyrimidinediones :

To an ice-cold solution of 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-methylphenyl) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinedione (0.62 g ; 0.002 mol) in dioxane (12 ml)-ethanol (25 ml) mixture containing sodium acetate (5 g),

was gradually added, a diazotised solution of *N*-phenylsulphanilamide (0.5 g; 0.002 mol) during stirring at 0-5° and the contents further stirred for 5 minutes. The reaction mixture was diluted with ice-cold water and the red coloured compound which separated out was filtered, washed with water, dried and had m.p. 188°. *Pure 1-phenyl-3-(p-methylphenyl)-5-(N-phenyl p-sulphamylbenzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinedione* was crystallised

from glacial acetic acid-DMF-ethanol mixture as a shining red solid, m.p. 190°. (yield : 0.78 g ; 66%). (Found : C, 61.0 ; H, 4.2. $C_{29}H_{28}O_4N_8S_2$ requires C, 61.1 ; H, 4.0%).

Other 1,3-diaryl-5-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones were similarly prepared and are entered in Tables 1-4.

TABLE 1—1-PHENYL-3-(*p*-BROMOPHENYL)-5-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) DIHYDRO-2-THIOXO-4,6(1H,5H) PYRIMIDINEDIONES (Fig. 1 : X=H ; Y=*p*-methyl)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Antibacterial activity		
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
1.	H	>300	O	64	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8S_2$	+	++	+++
2.	Acetyl	291	YO	67	$C_{22}H_{19}O_5N_8S_2$	+	-	++
3.	Phenyl	190	SR	66	$C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_8S_2$	+	-	++
4.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	293	RO	62	$C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_8S_2$	++	-	++
5.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	202	SR	65	$C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_8S_2$	++	-	++
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	252	SRO	67	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8ClS_2$	-	+	-
7.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	248	RO	68	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8ClS_2$	+	-	-
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	283	B	70	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8ClS_2$	+	+	+
9.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	289	YB	72	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8BrS_2$	-	-	-
10.	Guanidyl	261	RB	64	$C_{24}H_{21}O_4N_7S_2$	-	+	++
11.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	>300	O	69	$C_{27}H_{21}O_4N_8S_2$	+	-	-
12.	2,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-4-yl	285	SON	65	$C_{29}H_{25}O_4N_8S_2$	-	-	-
13.	4,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl	285	YO	72	$C_{29}H_{25}O_4N_8S_2$	++	-	-
14.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	277	O	62	$C_{29}H_{25}O_6N_8S_2$	++	-	++
15.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	>300	RB	68	$C_{28}H_{23}O_4N_8S_2$	+++	-	+

TABLE 2—1-PHENYL-3-(*p*-BROMOPHENYL)-5-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) DIHYDRO-2-THIOXO-4,6(1H,5H) PYRIMIDINEDIONES (Fig. 1 : X=H ; Y=*p*-Bromo)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Antibacterial activity		
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
1.	H	>300	OR	67	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8BrS_2$	-	-	-
2.	Acetyl	>300	Y	70	$C_{22}H_{19}O_5N_8BrS_2$	+	-	-
3.	Phenyl	265	SOR	66	$C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_8BrS_2$	-	-	-
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	233	RO	63	$C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_8BrS_2$	+	+	+
5.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	>300	O	65	$C_{23}H_{21}O_4N_8BrS_2$	-	-	-
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	260	O	68	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8BrS_2$	-	-	-
7.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	197	RO	65	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8ClBrS_2$	-	-	-
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	205	O	74	$C_{22}H_{19}O_4N_8SClBrS_2$	-	-	-
9.	Guanidyl	>300	O	66	$C_{24}H_{21}O_4N_7BrS_2$	-	-	-
10.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	>300	OB	73	$C_{28}H_{23}O_4N_7BrS_2$	+	-	-
11.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	>300	RB	69	$C_{28}H_{23}O_4N_7BrS_2$	+	-	-

TABLE 3—1,3-Bis(*p*-BROMOPHENYL)-5-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p* SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO) DIHYDRO-2-THIOXO-4,6(1H,5H) PYRIMIDINEDIONES (Fig. 1 : X=Y=*p*-Bromo)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Antibacterial activity		
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
1.	H	297	O	70	$C_{32}H_{25}O_4N_8Br_2S_2$	-	-	-
2.	Acetyl	>300	Y	71	$C_{32}H_{25}O_5N_8Br_2S_2$	-	-	-
3.	Phenyl	286-7	YO	68	$C_{33}H_{27}O_4N_8Br_2S_2$	+	-	+
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	201	OSN	65	$C_{33}H_{27}O_4N_8Br_2S_2$	-	-	-
5.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	282	YO	67	$C_{33}H_{27}O_4N_8Br_2S_2$	+	+	-
6.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	>300	Y	69	$C_{33}H_{27}O_4N_8Br_2S_2$	++	+	-
7.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	>300	BR	75	$C_{32}H_{25}O_4N_8ClBr_2S_2$	++	-	-
8.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	>300	BR	75	$C_{32}H_{25}O_4N_8Br_3S_2$	-	-	+++
9.	α -Pyridyl	>300	BO	68	$C_{32}H_{25}O_4N_8Br_2S_2$	-	-	+
10.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	>300	B	74	$C_{38}H_{29}O_4N_7Br_2S_2$	++	-	+++
11.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	>300	O	70	$C_{38}H_{29}O_4N_7Br_2S_2$	-	-	++

TABLE 4—1-(*p*-BROMOPHENYL)-3-(*p*-METHYLPHENYL)-5-(*N*-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENE AZO) DIHYDRO-2-THIOXO-4,6 (1H,5H)-PYRIMIDINEDIONES
(Fig. 1 : X=*p*-Bromo ; Y=*p*-methyl)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Antibacterial activity		
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
1.	H	297	SRO	66	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	+	+	-
2.	Acetyl	295	YO	69	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	+	-	-
3.	Phenyl	293	SOF	67	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	+	-	-
4.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	293	SO	64	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	++	-	+
5.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	285	O	67	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	++	-	-
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	268	SRO	66	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₇ ClBrS ₂	-	-	+
7.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	270	SO	69	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₇ ClBrS ₂	+	+	-
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	>300	SRO	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₇ ClBrS ₂	++	-	+
9.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	>300	RO	73	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₇ Br ₂ S ₂	-	-	+
10.	Guanidyl	267	RB	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	-	-	+
11.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	>300	O	71	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	+++	++	++++
12.	2,6-Dimethoxypyrimidin-4-yl	269	Y	64	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₇ BrS ₂	-	-	++
13.	5-Methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl	>300	Y	78	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₇ BrS ₂	-	-	++

There was good agreement between the C, H found and required.

B=Brown ; N=Needles ; O=Orange ; S=Shining ; R=Red ; Y=Yellow.

All the synthesised compounds were later subjected to *in vitro* screening against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* at two different concentrations 250 ug/ml and 500 ug/ml. The results of screening at the concentration of 250 ug/ml indicated that the title compounds exhibited higher activity against *S. aureus* and *P. pyocyanea* as compared to that against *E. coli*. Amongst all, the compounds of 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-bromophenyl)-5-(*N*-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzene-azo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones series exhibited very meagre activity against all the three micro-organisms. When these results

are compared with those reported earlier¹, it is evident that the introduction of the sulphonamide residue enhances the activity.

References

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